

POLITICAL SCIENCES

CRISIS MANAGEMENT AND POLITICAL RISK: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GERB IN BULGARIA AND CDU IN GERMANY DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, a global crisis that challenged governments across the world, also introduced significant political risks. For ruling parties, managing the crisis effectively became a test of political stability, public trust, and communication skills. This study focuses on two center-right political parties that were in power during the onset of the pandemic: GERB (Citizens for European Development of Bulgaria) in Bulgaria and CDU (Christian Democratic Union) in Germany. Both parties share a long-standing partnership and similar conservative values, making them suitable for comparison in crisis management. This paper aims to compare the crisis communication strategies and political risks faced by GERB and CDU, particularly in how they handled public health messaging, policy responses, and their political fallout from the COVID-19 pandemic.

GERB and CDU, as the ruling parties during the pandemic, were confronted with the daunting task of managing both the health crisis and its associated political risks. The pandemic's duration and impact forced governments to adopt a range of crisis communication strategies, implement severe policy interventions, and address public dissatisfaction in real-time. The objective of this study is to provide a comparative analysis of how these two political parties responded to the pandemic crisis, focusing on their communication strategies, policy responses, public reactions, and the long-term political implications of their management efforts. This publication is carried out within the framework of a research project funded by the UNWE R&D Fund, with reference number NI-18/2020, entitled: "The Covid-19 pandemic as a political risk: analysis and impact assessment"

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyze and compare the communication strategies used by GERB and CDU during the pandemic.
- To assess the policy responses including lockdown measures, economic aids, and healthcare system adjustments by both parties.
- To evaluate the public reaction, criticisms, and subsequent political impact of pandemic management on GERB and CDU.

Effective communication during a crisis is critical in managing public perception, maintaining trust, and ensuring compliance with public health measures. Both GERB and CDU were tasked with disseminating information, explaining policies, and justifying restrictive

measures during the pandemic. Their strategies, however, differed significantly due to variations in political culture, leadership styles, and public expectations.

In Bulgaria, GERB's communication strategy was largely dominated by Prime Minister Boyko Borissov, who relied on frequent public appearances and media announcements. Borissov's direct approach, while initially seen as an attempt to reassure the public, faced criticism for a lack of transparency and inconsistencies in messaging. Communication from the Bulgarian government often lacked clear, science-based explanations, which led to a decline in public trust as the pandemic progressed. Additionally, GERB faced challenges in leveraging digital platforms effectively. While social media channels, such as Facebook, were used to engage the public, the content often failed to target vulnerable groups or offer detailed updates, leading to further public dissatisfaction. This lack of targeted crisis communication contributed to growing skepticism about the government's handling of the pandemic (Valchanov, 2022)

The Bulgarian government's transparency issues were exacerbated by the spread of misinformation and rumors regarding healthcare responses, lockdown measures, and vaccination plans. Despite attempts to control the narrative through state-owned media, Borissov's government struggled to provide clear, cohesive messaging that could counteract public fears and anxieties. This deficiency in communication not only heightened public mistrust but also fueled opposition movements that would later impact GERB's political standing.

In contrast, Angela Merkel's leadership in Germany was marked by a calm, rational, and scientifically grounded communication approach. From the onset of the pandemic, Merkel emphasized the importance of basing decisions on data and expert advice, frequently referencing updates from the Robert Koch Institute, Germany's leading public health institute. Merkel's speeches were often sober, fact-driven, and aimed at encouraging public compliance with health measures. The use of scientific data and clear explanations of government decisions helped build and maintain trust, at least in the early stages of the pandemic. However, even in Germany, public patience began to wear thin as the pandemic dragged on and the vaccine rollout was delayed due to EU procurement challenges. (Wodak, 2021)

Merkel's government also adopted a collaborative communication strategy, involving regional leaders in decision-making processes. This decentralized approach allowed for tailored responses to the pandemic,

though it also created some inconsistencies across Germany's federal states. Nevertheless, Merkel's reliance on scientific discourse, combined with her measured public addresses, helped to manage public expectations more effectively than in Bulgaria. Despite criticisms regarding the slow vaccine rollout, Merkel's communication strategy largely succeeded in maintaining a higher degree of public trust compared to GERB's efforts in Bulgaria. (Pereira, 2021)

Both GERB and CDU were faced with unprecedented challenges in terms of policy response during the pandemic. The effectiveness of their measures in handling lockdowns, healthcare preparedness, and vaccination rollout significantly impacted their political standing.

In March 2020, Bulgaria and Germany both implemented strict lockdown measures, but the timing and scope of these restrictions varied. Bulgaria's GERB-led government enacted early, nationwide lockdowns, closing schools, businesses, and restricting movement. The healthcare system, however, was not adequately prepared to handle the surge in COVID-19 cases, leading to significant public dissatisfaction as hospitals became overwhelmed. (Spirova, 2021) The economic fallout was severe, with unemployment rates rising and businesses struggling to survive under prolonged restrictions. Despite government promises of economic relief, many citizens felt that the support was insufficient, contributing to public unrest.

Germany, under CDU leadership, took a more measured approach, initially allowing federal states to implement their own restrictions. However, as the pandemic worsened, Merkel pushed for more coordinated nationwide measures, leading to stricter lockdowns in late 2020. Germany's healthcare system was better equipped to handle the crisis, with higher ICU capacity and more extensive testing infrastructure. However, the decentralized approach sometimes led to confusion, as restrictions varied from state to state. Merkel's government also provided substantial economic relief packages, which helped mitigate some of the economic impacts of the lockdowns. (Pereira, 2021)

One of the most critical aspects of pandemic management was the vaccine rollout. Germany faced early delays in vaccine distribution due to the EU's centralized procurement process, which frustrated the public and led to declining approval ratings for CDU. Despite these delays, Germany eventually ramped up its vaccination campaign, relying on its robust healthcare infrastructure to ensure widespread access to vaccines. (Warren, 2021)

In contrast, Bulgaria struggled with significant vaccine hesitancy. Misinformation, distrust in the healthcare system, and a lack of clear government messaging all contributed to low vaccination rates. By mid-2021, Bulgaria had one of the lowest vaccination rates in the EU, further undermining public confidence in GERB's pandemic management. (Holst, 2020) The government's inability to counteract vaccine hesitancy and implement an effective vaccination campaign would later play a significant role in GERB's declining political fortunes.

Public reactions to the pandemic policies of GERB and CDU varied widely, influenced by the perceived effectiveness of their crisis management efforts.

The Bulgarian public's response to GERB's pandemic management was largely negative. Public protests erupted in mid-2020, fueled by dissatisfaction with the government's handling of the healthcare system and the economic fallout from prolonged lockdowns. (Spirova, 2021) Additionally, allegations of corruption and mismanagement further eroded public trust in Borissov's leadership. The opposition parties and media played a significant role in amplifying these criticisms, with frequent accusations of government inefficiency and failure to protect citizens' livelihoods. As a result, GERB faced a sharp decline in support heading into the 2021 elections.

In Germany, the public's initial response to CDU's pandemic management was largely positive. Merkel's science-based communication and Germany's strong healthcare system helped maintain a sense of stability during the early stages of the pandemic. However, as the pandemic continued and frustrations over the slow vaccine rollout grew, public approval of CDU began to wane. The media and opposition parties criticized the government for its delays in securing vaccines and for inconsistent messaging regarding restrictions. Despite these criticisms, Merkel's personal approval ratings remained relatively stable, reflecting her long-standing reputation as a steady and reliable leader. (Wodak, 2021)

The political consequences of the pandemic for GERB and CDU were profound. Both parties saw shifts in their political standing as a result of their crisis management efforts.

By the time of the 2021 elections, GERB's support had significantly declined. The combination of public dissatisfaction with the government's handling of the healthcare crisis, economic instability, and allegations of corruption led to a loss of trust in Borissov's leadership. While GERB managed to remain a key player in Bulgarian politics, its weakened position underscored the long-term political risks of mishandling the pandemic. (Spirova, 2021)

CDU also faced political consequences due to the pandemic, although the impact was less severe than in Bulgaria. Merkel's decision to step down as chancellor in 2021 opened the door for a new leadership transition within the CDU, and while the party remained a dominant force in German politics, the challenges of the pandemic highlighted weaknesses in crisis management that the new leadership would need to address. The vaccine rollout delays and public frustration over prolonged restrictions contributed to CDU's electoral performance in 2021, marking the beginning of a new political era in Germany. (Warren, 2021)

In comparing the crisis management strategies of GERB in Bulgaria and CDU in Germany during the COVID-19 pandemic, several key differences emerge. While both parties faced significant challenges, the effectiveness of their communication strategies and policy responses varied. GERB's failure to maintain transparency and address public concerns effectively led to a sharp decline in support, while CDU's science-based

approach helped mitigate some of the political risks associated with the pandemic, despite frustrations over vaccine delays. The long-term implications of the pandemic on political risk for both parties underscore the importance of effective crisis management in maintaining political stability during global crises.

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